

AdvanCing behavioural
Change Through
an INclusive Green deal

Operational guidelines and recommendations for an Inclusive European Green Deal – 2nd Cycle

European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)

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List of acronyms

ANCT	French National Agency for the Cohesion of Territories
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
CS	Civil Society
CCTV	Closed Circuit Television
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CFP	Common Food Policy
EOS	Elinor-Ostrom Siedlungsprojekt
EEG	Erneuerbare Energien Gesetz
ETF	European Transport Workers' Federation
EU	European Union
FSTP	Financial Support for Third Parties
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
GBV	Gender-based Violence
GD	Green Deal
IEMD	Internal Energy Market Directive
UITP	International Association of Public Transport
IPBES	International Panel of Experts on Sustainable Food Systems
ITF	International Transport Forum
NGO	Non-Government Organisation
OS	Open Studio
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
RL	Research Line
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
VRT NWS	Vlaamse Radio- en Televisieomroeporganisatie News
WP	Work Package
YRS	Young Researchers of Serbia

The ACCTING project

It is acknowledged by now that the global climate crisis is not only an ecological crisis but also an economic, social and political crisis, with devastating effects on individuals and societies. These negative effects are not evenly distributed within societies. It is the poorer, marginalised and vulnerable groups who are the most acutely affected, exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities. The European Green Deal foresees efficient use of resources for a circular and clean economy. However, inequalities emerge in the context of its policy and interventions.

The EU-funded ACCTING project takes these considerations as a starting point for a complex series of research and experimental activities aimed at identifying, analysing and testing policies and initiatives capable of responding to this crisis, mitigating its effects on the most vulnerable and helping them play a significant role in the pursuit of greater environmental sustainability.

The project mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies and supporting behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

ACCTING explores the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate policy responses and potential negative influences, and mitigate such impacts in decision-making. The project collects new data on Green Deal policy interventions and co-designs and implements pilot actions to reduce or prevent policy-related inequalities and advance behavioural change for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal.

Project consortium

	European Science Foundation (ESF)
	Örebro University (ORU)
 YELLOW WINDOW	Yellow Window (YW)
	Knowledge and Innovation (K&I)
	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation (ZSI)
	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)
	ICLEI - Local Governments for Sustainability, European Secretariat
	Sabancı University (SU)
	Instituto de Geografia e Ordenamento de Território (IGOT)
	South East European Research Center (SEERC)
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Summary

This deliverable comprises a set of policy recommendations presented as a series of tailored factsheets designed for two primary target groups: policymakers and civil society organisations, but also other relevant stakeholders such as transport operators, media and academics. These recommendations are based on insights gained during the second research cycle of ACCTING. The document provides a comprehensive account of the process undertaken to develop these recommendations.

Introduction

This WP5 deliverable takes into account the research results from the ACCTING project's second research cycle, as well as its pilot actions and Open Studios. More specifically, insights from the eight research lines from WP3, four Open Studios part of WP4 and ten pilot actions part of WP5 were utilised for this deliverable. Inspiring bottom-up initiatives¹ mapped in WP2 are also included here as “better stories.” The deliverable presents operational guidelines and recommendations developed in the form of factsheets for the target groups, such as policymakers, civil society organisations, NGOs, and other relevant actors in the field. Nevertheless, some factsheets in the deliverable provide recommendations to a diverse set of actors, as the topics addressed need attention of multiple stakeholders concurrently.

Seven factsheets are developed in this cycle, focused on topics such as: safety in public transportation for women and socially vulnerable groups, integration of wellbeing into policy mechanism to foster inclusivity and equality, exploring resistance as a crucial component of transformative change, redefining the notion of public interest, promoting innovative policies to support commons, public civil society partnerships for behavioural change, and the role of commons in driving inclusive behavioural change.

Each factsheet includes a brief introduction to the topic, insights from ACCTING's research that highlight on-the-ground inequalities, followed by a set of actionable recommendations. They also feature inspiring stories – “better stories” – showcasing effective practices that help address these inequalities and conclude with an overview of the specific Green Deal policy areas directly related to the topic.

As a part of the communication and dissemination strategy, these factsheets are aimed at informing policymakers at local, regional, and transnational levels, civil society organisations, non-government organisations working for vulnerable and marginalised groups, and other stakeholders such as academics and the media. The focus is on improving Green Deal policies, such that a further increase in inequalities can be prevented. ACCTING research in both first and second cycles has highlighted the need to complement the Green Deal with policy actions at European and national level. In particular, to address vulnerabilities and prevent inequalities.

¹ Carnevale, A., Pellegrini Masini, G., Klöckner, C. A., Altınay, A. G., Düzel, E., Türel, B. B., Kerremans, A., Alain Denis, & Cacace, M. (2023). ACCTING D2.2 - Report on inspiring practice cases. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7711880>

Methodology

Below you can find the process of development of policy recommendations:

- Bottom-up initiatives mapped as a part of WP2 in the first cycle of ACCTING in 27 member states, the UK, Türkiye, Serbia, Norway, Japan, USA and Brazil are utilised as better stories in the operational guidelines and recommendations developed as factsheets.
- Research activity in WP3, conducted within the 13 countries across eight thematic research lines also provided inputs to the factsheets. In this cycle WP3 implemented quasi-experimental studies which combined real-life interventions with qualitative interviews, quantitative surveys, and participatory observations, informed the Open Studios (OS) WP4, a hands-on series of workshops with consortium members and external experts
- In preparation of the OS, taking inputs from the available results of the second research cycle, a thematic workshop was held on 3 September, 2024 among the consortium members. This workshop was helpful in shortlisting eight themes for the OS. At the end of the workshop voting was done by the consortium members to select themes for the OS. Eventually, four themes emerged as winners to be further carried out as four OS:
 - Mobility justice and sustainable transition
 - From pilot project to sustainable social change
 - Transformative resistance: engaging with marginalised groups to co-create a just green transition
 - Reimagining commons for inclusive transitions in our livelihoods
- In conclusion of the OS, a decision was made based on the participants' vote on the seven action ideas to be further developed into policy recommendations (i.e., factsheets) for policymakers (at all levels), civil society organisations, community groups, media, academics and other relevant stakeholders such as transport and mobility operators.
- For the seven factsheets, two action ideas (Wellbeing as trigger for behavioural change and towards safer mobility – A holistic approach to tackling violence in public transportation) were generated from OS1 (i.e., Mobility justice and sustainable transition) also the focus of RL7² and RL8³ of ACCTING.
- Similarly, two action ideas (Transformative resistance for a just and inclusive Green Deal and Resisting narrow vision of public interest) emerged from the cross-cutting theme of OS3 (i.e., Transformative resistance: engaging with marginalised groups to co-create a just green transition)

² Please see RL7: <https://accting.eu/research-lines/research-line-7-transport-poverty-and-sustainable-travel-families-in-socially-vulnerable-areas/>

³ Please see RL8 info: <https://accting.eu/research-lines/research-line-8-post-lockdown-sustainable-mobilities-centering-cycling-and-walking/>

- Two further action ideas (Promoting policy innovations that promote commons and Public civil society partnerships for behavioural change) stemmed from OS4 (i.e., Reimagining commons for inclusive transitions in our livelihoods).
- Also, one further action idea (Public civil society partnerships for behavioural change) emerged from ACCTING's experience of implementing 10 pilot actions (WP5) at the local level in seven countries and OS2 (i.e., From pilot project to sustainable social change)
- After the topics for the factsheets were decided, working groups were created to draft the factsheets. Then, each factsheet was reviewed by the Advisory Board members of ACCTING. In addition, one factsheet was also reviewed by a Sister Project member.
- After receiving the feedback from the reviewers, each working group addressed all the necessary comments and finalised the factsheets.
- Subsequently, the factsheets will be advocated among the target groups as a part of the Advocacy Plan of WP7

Policy recommendations

In the table below you can find an overview of the policy recommendations presented as seven factsheets with their target groups.

Factsheets	Target groups
Towards safer mobility – A holistic approach to tackling violence in public transportation	Policymakers (local, national and European level) and transport operators
Wellbeing as a trigger for behavioural change	Policymakers, civil society organisations, transport and mobility providers and academic institutions
Transformative resistance for a just and inclusive European Green Deal	Policymakers (local, national and European level)
Resisting narrow vision of public interest	Civil society organisations and policy makers ((local, national and European level)
Promoting policy innovations that promote commons	Policy makers (local, national and European level)
Public civil society partnerships for behavioural change	Local government and civil society organisations
Commons for all	Non-government organisations

Table 1: Overview of factsheets

Towards safer mobility

A holistic approach to tackling violence in public transportation

Authors: Arne Nys (YW), Marina Cacace (K&I), Alain Denis (YW)

Summary

- Violence in public transport is a widespread issue affecting both users and workers, with research showing three in five women globally report experiencing sexual harassment (Social Development Direct, 2020). This is more than twice what is reported in general life by women (FRA, EIGE, & Eurostat, 2024). Despite this prevalence, transport operators and policymakers frequently overlook gender-based violence in their safety planning.
- ACCTING's research reveals that vulnerable groups often face heightened risks, leading them to modify travel patterns, choose alternative transport modes, or avoid travel entirely. Women in particular report adopting defensive strategies like carefully selecting seating positions, avoiding certain routes, or restricting travel times.
- Local, national, and international policymakers need a consistent framework to address these systemic challenges. The UniSAFE⁴ 7P model, validated across multiple sectors, provides a comprehensive approach spanning from prevalence assessment to policy implementation.
- Recommendations to tackle gender-based violence effectively include, among others, systematic collection of gender-disaggregated incident data, comprehensive staff training and victim support systems, and establishment of coordinated response protocols between transport operators, law enforcement, and support services.
- Case studies across Europe demonstrate that successful interventions require strong partnerships between transport operators, law enforcement, community organisations, and support services, combined with sustained investment in both infrastructure and human resources.

⁴ [UniSAFE D3.1 Theoretical and conceptual framework](#)

Introduction

Violence in transport is a complex, systemic societal problem, influenced by factors such as transport mode, social context, time of day, and the journey's stages from door to door. Current efforts to address it are dispersed lacking holistic, user-centred approaches. While the focus tends to be on other criminal acts such as vandalism and terrorism, gender-based violence (GBV) is often overlooked despite the significant impact it has on mobility patterns and especially on the lives of people in vulnerable conditions exposed to a higher risk of violence. Public transport operators, key players in preventing and addressing violence, are also victims of it. In Belgium, for example, there are 15 cases of violence against transport workers every day (VRT NWS, 2024). This affects both individuals and services, causing disruptions and reducing reliability. At the EU level, the social partners (trade unions and employers) have a 20-year history of working together to tackle this phenomenon. They have been addressing this concern by issuing joint recommendations to transport operators, covering the role of employers in their human resource policy (e.g., harassment) and what is called “third party” violence (UITP & ITF, 2020).

Findings from ACCTING

ACCTING's findings are all from a user perspective, with a strong focus on gender-based violence and harassment.

- Everyday violence is widespread on public transport. This is still largely undocumented, although those who are more exposed to violence are aware of how widespread it is. The common complaints among women are about leers in public transportation, unintentional touching or groping from fellow transport users.
- Everyday violence may develop into more serious forms of violence. In certain areas, circumstances or times of day, harassment can escalate into sexual assault, bullying or robbery. Those at risk are forced to adopt preventive strategies such as avoiding isolated areas, avoiding drunk people, or in general opting for a taxi rather than a bus.
- The risk of violence leads to changes in mobility behaviours. In many cases, women are pushed to abandon public transport and use private cars as much as possible, which they see as safer. In some cases, biking is seen as a better option than public transport.
- Sometimes the risk of violence restricts access to mobility altogether. Those who feel more vulnerable to violence on public transport and who do not have the option of using other means of transport limit their mobility or, if they cannot do so for lack of other means, are forced to accept the exposure to risky situations.
- The link between violence and mobility is largely overlooked. Public authorities tend to regard harassment and petty crime (e.g., pickpocketing) as almost inevitable in

public transport systems. The gender perspective is rarely considered, and the phenomenon remains underestimated.

Recommendations

ACCTING's recommendation is to apply UniSAFE's 7P model⁵ in the context of public transport, looking at the entire journey of the user from door-to-door. This model provides a holistic framework for understanding and combating gender-based violence in various domains. At the same time, this model resonates with ACCTING's findings which highlight the complexity of causes, its manifestations and possible solutions to the issue of violence in transportation.

The model allows policymakers and operators to develop comprehensive solutions that can combat all forms of violence that both users and staff are experiencing. It provides this along seven key dimensions: Prevalence, Prevention, Protection, Prosecution, Provision of services, Partnerships, and Policies.

By considering all seven dimensions, transportation providers and policymakers can develop more effective and comprehensive strategies to ensure safe mobility for all users. Below, we have summarised a non-exhaustive list of measures that can be taken within each dimension to start tackling violence in transportation. While these are based on successful case studies and previous research, they are suggested examples, not a final set of instructions to follow.

Transport providers can use these as a starting point for an open conversation about how to design their own action plan while involving their local stakeholders and partners.

1. Prevalence: Understanding the extent and nature of the violence

- Transport data reveals a gap in safety monitoring. The lack of specifically gender-disaggregated data and ineffective reporting systems hampers efforts to understand and address the issue. Conduct regular, participatory safety audits involving diverse user groups to identify high-risk areas, times, and patterns.
- Create user-friendly and accessible reporting mechanisms, such as apps or hotlines, ensuring anonymity and confidentiality.
- Introduce surveys to assess underreporting and refine reporting mechanisms.
- Establish mandatory gender-disaggregated data collection systems for transport operators.

⁵ [UniSAFE D3.1 Theoretical and conceptual framework](#)

2. Prevention: Implementing measures to stop violence before it occurs

- Redesign infrastructure to enhance safety, including improved lighting, clear sightlines, and visible CCTV systems.
- Include gender-sensitivity and awareness training mandatorily in curricula for all transport and subcontracted staff.
- Launch zero tolerance public awareness campaigns targeting both potential perpetrators and bystanders, to encourage intervention.
- Implement request-stop programmes during off-peak hours to minimise exposure to unsafe environments.

3. Protection: Ensuring safety and support for victims and bystanders

- Increase the visible presence of trained security personnel, especially during high-risk times.
- Equip stations and vehicles with panic buttons and emergency call systems linked to rapid response teams.
- Ensure access to 24/7 helplines staffed by trained professionals to assist victims and witnesses.

4. Prosecution: Taking legal and disciplinary action against perpetrators

- Establish clear protocols for first responders and judicial processes to ensure swift action against perpetrators.
- Develop specialised gender-based violence units within existing transport police or security teams.
- Deploy technology such as body cameras and evidence collection tools to strengthen cases and improve judicial outcomes.

5. Provision of services: Offering support services for victims and survivors

- Offer immediate psychological support and legal aid through trained staff or external partnerships.
- Create advocacy programmes to help victims navigate legal and recovery processes.
- Provide workplace support services for transport workers facing violence, including trauma counselling.

6. Partnerships: Cooperating with relevant stakeholders and organisations

- Facilitate collaboration between transport operators, law enforcement, women's and LGBTQI+ NGOs, and community organisations to align and evaluate interventions.
- Engage local governments and advocacy groups to co-design transport safety policies and initiatives.
- Partner with educational institutions to develop inclusive urban mobility training programmes.

7. Policies: Developing comprehensive strategies and formal commitments

- Establish uniform minimum safety standards across transport modes, ensuring consistent implementation.
- Require operators to include safety clauses in procurement contracts, including staff training and infrastructure upgrades.
- Enact comprehensive national and regional policies explicitly addressing gender-based violence in transportation.

Better Stories

Col·lectiu Punt 6^{6,7}

This is a Barcelona-based feminist collective that aims to rethink urban spaces from a gender perspective. In the past 5 years, they have regularly conducted exploratory walks and bike rides with local women to audit urban spaces and transportation systems through a gender lens. These walks have identified safety concerns, accessibility issues, and areas needing improvement. For example, the results of their exploratory bike rides in Barcelona helped to inform design decisions for the Bicing bike network. They also offer training programmes aimed at urban professionals and public officials to teach them how to analyse urban spaces from a gendered perspective, covering topics like participatory design methods and inclusive public spaces. The collective's safety audit of the public transportation network has led the local transport operator FGC to implement an action plan on tackling perceived safety in their stations.

⁶ Col·lectiu Punt 6 - Urbanisme feminista per a la vida quotidiana

⁷ <https://www.punt6.org/project-portfolio/auditoria-de-seguretat-amb-perspectiva-de-gener-a-estacions-de-ferrocarrils-de-la-generalitat-de-catalunya/>

Île-de-France^{8,9} – Public transport anti-harassment campaign

In 2018, the Île-de-France Region started a safety initiative to combat sexual harassment in public transportation. The programme combined increased human presence (785 specifically trained new security agents), an easy-to-use emergency alert system (3117), and more visible emergency call points. A trial was run with a bus stop-on-request service after 22:00 on select routes, allowing passengers to exit between regular stops, reducing walking distance in dark hours. The interventions were integrated into a widespread public awareness campaign that called on bystanders to intervene or call for help, while targeted safety improvements are being taken up into long-running infrastructure investment programmes.

Train operator Italo partners with police to provide self-defence and de-escalation training to staff^{10,11}

An Italian private train operator Italo has implemented multiple safety initiatives, including police partnerships and comprehensive training programmes. Since 2017, they partner with the railway police to have uniformed officers present on their trains as a resource for passengers and crew. In 2022, they launched a women's safety programme together with the telephone helpline Telefono Rosa, providing Krav Maga self-defence training to over 400 female employees and women in domestic violence shelters as a part of their integrated empowerment strategy. This was further expanded in 2023 into a broader safety training programme for over 620 on-board staff of all genders including train managers and attendants, focusing on strategies for recognising warning signs of hostile behaviour that could escalate into verbal or physical aggression, as well as practical self-defence training.

Relevant policy areas

These recommendations are linked to the following policy areas:

- The European Parliament resolution on ensuring European transportation works for women
- The European Union's Green Deal policy on transport and the mobility sector
- The EU Directive on combating violence against women and domestic violence
- The Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence against Women and Domestic Violence (commonly referred to as the Istanbul Convention)

⁸ <https://charter-equality.eu/exemple-de-bonnes-pratiques/ile-de-france-public-transport-anti-harassment-campaign.html>

⁹ [Press dossier on sexual harassment and violence](#)

¹⁰ [Italo employees get trained on safety by Railway Police](#)

¹¹ [Italo employees learn self-defence](#)

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Further readings

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Wellbeing as a trigger for behavioural change

Authors: Dilay Çelebi Gonidis (SEERC), Aart Kerremans (YW), Nikita Sharma (ECSA)

Summary

Wellbeing can act as a pivotal driver for behavioural change, leveraging the principles of inclusivity under the Green Deal framework. Evidence from ACCTING's research shows that active transportation, sustainable food systems, and nature-based interventions not only enhance individual health but also foster community resilience and social cohesion. These findings confirm and expand upon existing research (WHO, 2016, 2018, 2020; European Commission, 2019, 2020), showing that changes motivated by wellbeing are more likely to be adopted and sustained, especially if they also address social and cultural factors. However, ACCTING's results emphasise that systemic barriers such as financial constraints, limited infrastructure, and cultural mismatches hinder vulnerable groups from participating in these transformative practices. Findings from ACCTING pilot projects demonstrate how inclusive strategies, like community gardens and cycling programmes, can address these barriers while inspiring change through relatable stories and public campaigns. Moreover, pilot projects bring new evidence of how wellbeing considerations not only increase participation but also support social cohesion, addressing a knowledge gap on the intersection of social equity, health, and environmental sustainability. At the same time, it requires integrating wellbeing into policies, promoting accessible transportation, supporting community-driven initiatives, and using storytelling to inspire collective action.

Introduction

Wellbeing is increasingly appearing in public policy dialogues, with some governments and institutions using it as a lens to measure prosperity “beyond growth” or as a near-synonym for SDG-related goals (OECD, 2020; Fioramonti, 2017). In ACCTING, we emphasise wellbeing to mean the mental and physical health benefits and social connectedness that individuals experience. By highlighting wellbeing, ACCTING focuses on the **intrinsic motivations** that encourage individuals and communities to pursue health-promoting and environmentally friendly behaviours, addressing a key gap in how social equity intersects with the Green Deal efforts.

Recent findings underscore the powerful connection between wellbeing, behavioural change, and physical health, highlighting their critical role in fostering inclusivity and equality within the Green Deal. ACCTING research findings show that **personal wellbeing (encompassing both mental and physical health) can serve as a significant motivator for adopting new behaviours.**

Behavioural change strategies under the Green Deal must recognise that wellbeing can act as a powerful driver for individual and collective behavioural change. **A shift in perception is vital**, for example:

- **Transportation must be redefined**, to be seen not only as a means of mobility, but also as **a space for physical activity and mindfulness**, where active travel supports both physical and mental health. For example, the awareness that active modes of transportation improve cardiovascular health and reduce anxiety can drive greater adoption of sustainable behaviour.
- **Sustainable dietary practices** (also put forward by the work of e.g., Bechthold, Boeing, Schwedhelm, Hoffman, Knüppel, Iqbal and Schwingshack, 2019; World Cancer Research Fund International, 2018) should be promoted not just for environmental benefits, but also for their **role in preventing chronic diseases and improving overall vitality.**

By embedding wellbeing-focused interventions into environmental and mobility policies, the Green Deal can achieve its dual goals of sustainability and social equity, ensuring that transformative change benefits all, particularly those in marginalised or disadvantaged situations.

Findings from ACCTING

Existing research has long demonstrated that economic constraints significantly affect people's ability to adopt healthier and more sustainable diets. Studies such as Capstick et al. (2022) highlight those individuals with limited income often focus on affordability over health or sustainability, contributing to lower rates of pro-environmental behaviours. Civil society organisations (CSOs) have built on these findings to encourage supermarkets to offer lower-cost organic products — an example of how evidence-based advocacy can shape market trends (Parekh and Klintman, 2021).

Findings from ACCTING's research line 6 (Values associated with Environmentally Sustainable Food Consumption) confirms this pattern showing that **changing food values could lead to behavioural change in food consumption.** Specifically, food values relating to animal welfare (e.g., pain-free production), environmental welfare (e.g., is produced without disturbing the balance of nature), and health (e.g., is good for my skin, teeth, hair, nails, etc.) showed the strongest correlations with sustainable (seasonal and plant-based food) food consumption. However, our findings also show that **economic barriers heavily influence food-related behavioural change and access to sustainable options.** Income disparities influence food values and consumption patterns, with low-

income groups prioritising affordability over health, wellbeing and sustainability; thus, consuming fewer plant-based foods.

The second key finding from this research line is that **participation in bottom-up initiatives (BUIs)** is associated with **change towards giving greater importance to health and environmental (animal welfare) food values, as well as to consuming more environmentally sustainable food (seasonal and plant-based)**. People who reported greater participation in different kinds of food- and environment-related activism and social movements more often report that they value food that is produced in environmentally sustainable, socially just, and animal-friendly ways.

ACCTING's research lines 7 and 8 on transport poverty and sustainable travel similarly highlight the critical role of wellbeing in promoting behavioural change towards sustainable mobility, particularly among vulnerable populations. **Transitioning from motorised vehicles to active mobility options contributes to reduced stress, improved physical activity, and enhanced social connectivity**. However, structural barriers, such as inadequate infrastructure, high transportation costs, and safety concerns disproportionately impact economically and socially marginalised groups, limiting their ability to participate in these practices. These challenges are particularly evident in regions with insufficient public transport systems or cycling networks.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are based on the results from ACCTING's research and co-creation workshops. They are primarily targeted towards policymakers (local, regional, national, and EU level). However, several recommendations are also relevant for civil society organisations, community groups, transport and mobility providers, and academic institutions:

- **Integrate wellbeing metrics into policy frameworks**

Policies can benefit from incorporating wellbeing metrics to better address the interconnected challenges of health, environmental sustainability, and social equity. Research demonstrates that integrating wellbeing into policy frameworks, such as urban mobility plans and environmental programmes, can create co-benefits for public health and environmental sustainability (Chapman and Howden-Chapman, 2021). For example, urban mobility plans can include metrics such as **reductions in cardio-vascular and stress-related illnesses and increased physical activity levels**. While environmental programmes can measure improvements in **community cohesion and emotional resilience**, alongside emission reductions. This approach not only aligns with decarbonisation goals but also ensures that wellbeing improvements are integral to measuring the success of sustainability initiatives.

- **Promote active and accessible transportation with a focus on wellbeing**

Comprehensive networks of pedestrian pathways, cycling lanes and affordable public transit systems play a significant role in supporting both physical and mental wellbeing. These infrastructures can be complemented by initiatives such as bike-sharing programmes, community walking groups, and active commuting campaigns that highlight benefits like stress reduction, improved fitness, and stronger social connections. Ensuring accessibility is also essential, with transport options tailored to meet the needs of vulnerable populations such as older adults, low-income groups, and caregivers. Such measures can promote independence, reduce mobility-related anxiety, and encourage equitable participation in sustainable practices. Communication tools such as mobility apps and other technological solutions, can complement these measures by providing personalised information on health benefits, e.g., calories burned or exposure to pollutants. This can further motivate individuals to adopt sustainable transportation choices (Marquart and Schuppan, 2021).

- **Foster cross-sectoral collaboration for sustainable wellbeing**

Integrated planning across sectors such as mobility, health, social welfare and environmental protection, can help create more cohesive and effective solutions. For example, linking active transportation policies with health promotion campaigns could encourage physical activity while reducing reliance on motorised vehicles. Multi-stakeholder platforms involving policymakers, businesses and NGOs can provide opportunities to co-design initiatives that address both environmental sustainability and wellbeing, ensuring a collaborative approach to meeting diverse community needs.

- **Support community-driven sustainability initiatives that promote wellbeing-focused campaigns**

Financial support, resources, and capacity-building workshops should be provided for grassroots projects like urban gardening, tree planting, and food-sharing programmes. As highlighted by Baker and colleagues (2024), these are effective ways to reduce eco-anxiety and foster social bonds. Moreover, they can help foster partnerships between local governments and community organisations to tackle multidimensional challenges such as food security, green space access, and social isolation.

- **Policies/actions should focus on improving the affordability and accessibility of sustainable food options**

To make sustainable food options accessible, especially for low-income groups, one option is subsidising plant-based and locally sourced foods and using wellbeing as a motivator for this policy change. To support this further, collaborating with community-driven initiatives like urban gardens and food literacy workshops can enhance social connections and raise awareness of the nutritional and emotional benefits of sustainable diets. Additionally, campaigns can emphasise the mental and physical advantages of nutritious and ecological food, including higher energy levels, reduced chronic disease risk, and increased life satisfaction. To successfully address diverse income groups, the messages can integrate

multiple values, like social justice, environmental sustainability and animal welfare, to make sustainable diets appealing and accessible to all.

Better Stories

In ACCTING, we look for inspiring bottom-up initiatives as ‘*better stories*’, a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis¹² to refer to promising practices that can instil ideas for how to advance individual and collective behavioural change as envisioned by the Green Deal. This factsheet focuses on better stories of bottom-up initiatives across Europe to highlight inclusive grassroots efforts that can inspire further initiatives and policies in turn.

Walk the City¹³ is a women-led ecological association in Prague concerned with the development of walking as a means of transport, air pollution, and the regulation of car traffic. Particularly since the COVID-19 pandemic, they have emphasised the importance of developing a walkable city. Initially, they were focused on women and the barriers they face in urban mobility, but in time this expanded to also include other groups. They advocate for the protection of pedestrians, in particular older people and children on their way to school, the promotion of walking as a healthy and sustainable means of transport, and the improvement of public spaces. An example of one of their actions consists of collaborating with schools to organise events where children and their parents are ‘challenged’ to walk to school as often as possible (e.g., in the span of one week), emphasising that “it is a great opportunity to move”. They support these kinds of events by trying to make streets and public spaces safer for children. In this way, behavioural change towards more sustainable mobility is promoted.

Sindikata Biciklista (Cyclists Union)¹⁴ is a Croatian NGO that organises various activities around mobility and cycling. Their goal is to improve bicycle-based mobility (and other sustainable forms) to facilitate the uptake of sustainable and healthy transport options. They promote healthy and sustainable forms of mobility, including cycling and walking, through activities like policy advocacy, promoting cycling culture, and carrying out educational campaigns. In their educational activities, they emphasise health benefits and teach ways to reduce tensions between cyclists and pedestrians (who are often competing for the same limited space) as well as how to combine cycling with public transport.

MindFood¹⁵ is an organisation in the United Kingdom that offers the opportunity to engage in food-growing activities (among other pursuits) to people struggling with mental health issues, with the goal of making edible gardening more inclusive and accessible, while being supportive of people’s overall (mental) wellbeing. Based in West London, the initiative engages in ecotherapy with people who either signed up themselves or were referred by a GP. The main activity that is offered consists of a six-week course consisting of weekly sessions that aim to reduce depression, stress and anxiety through edible gardening. After

¹² [Georgis, D. \(2013\). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.](#)

¹³ <https://peskymestem.cz/en/>

¹⁴ <https://sindikatabiciklista.hr/o-nama/>

¹⁵ <https://www.mindfood.org.uk/>

involvement in the programme, most participants are found to have implemented positive changes in their diets, and to display increases in (self-reported) wellbeing and physical health measurements.

Toques en stock¹⁶ is a French association that aims to organise regular cooking workshops to counter food insecurity among vulnerable segments of the population. These cooking workshops offer people access to healthy food and teach them how to cook their own, while minimising food waste by recycling afterwards. Target groups of the initiative include people (mostly women) who live in temporary emergency accommodation in the broader Paris region (i.e., refugees, people with very low or no income, survivors of trafficking or exploitation, etc.). This means that the recipes that are used are adapted to their limited circumstances in terms of available equipment.

Relevant Green Deal policy areas

- 1. Sustainable and smart mobility:** Promoting active transportation not only reduces emissions but also enhances physical and mental health through increased physical activity and reduced stress.
- 2. Farm to fork strategy:** Initiatives that make sustainable and nutritious food more accessible improve dietary health while fostering social inclusion.
- 3. Biodiversity and ecosystem protection:** Nature-based interventions restore ecosystems and promote emotional resilience by reconnecting individuals with nature.

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Transformative resistance for a just and inclusive European Green Deal

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Summary

The global climate crisis disproportionately affects marginalised and vulnerable populations, who bear the brunt of its ecological, economic, and social impacts. Yet these groups are not merely victims; they are key drivers of transformative change. Their practices of resistance, resilience, and sustainability provide vital, untapped resources for addressing the climate crisis and fostering social and behavioural shifts toward sustainability. Their resistance and resilience, often seen as barriers, should thus instead be recognised as sources of innovation. This requires agency of these communities and incorporating their contributions into policy decision-making processes. By centring on the voices and lived experiences of those most affected, policymakers can design inclusive strategies that address both climate justice and social equity.

Introduction

The Green Deal (GD) is intended to be inclusive and widely accepted as a joint societal goal. However, it encompasses policies which unevenly affect marginalised groups due to intersecting factors of marginalisation and disadvantage across policy areas. The sustainability programmes and action plans, guided by the GD, national programmes, and scientific discourses, increasingly include community-based and participatory methodologies. Notwithstanding, they often remain top-down, disconnected from the needs of communities, and lacking social justice and equity dimensions.

Social and political frictions emerge in the transition, and transformation programmes can hinder collaboration and lead to resistance to change or delay the implementation of the policies. Resistance refers to both everyday informal and covert actions by individuals, as well as to more organised collective and overt actions by groups or movements. Scholars have identified a rich *repertoire* of resistance, ranging from hesitation, avoidance, and foot-dragging, to strikes, demonstrations and noncompliance (Brink et al., 2023, p. 5-10). They

show resistance is complex, connected to the intersectional dynamics of marginalisation and globalisation.

The literature and the ACCTING research highlight that it is essential to recognise resistance as a legitimate, complex response to work with, rather than as a hurdle to overcome. It can **bring to the fore new insights into the effects of the transformation programmes**, as well as **conceptual and methodological innovations**.

By acknowledging and working with resistance, policymakers can uncover gaps in inclusivity, barriers to access, or mistrust stemming from marginalisation. This recognition can foster constructive dialogue and result in policies rooted in equality and justice.

Findings from ACCTING

The ACCTING project builds on large-scale European interdisciplinary research to address the complexities of behavioural and social change and find solutions for equitable and sustainable climate transitions. In the research, resistance manifests in diverse forms: as visible, organised, collective actions; and as subtle every day and unorganised forms, such as hesitation, noncompliance, or disengagement:

- Marginalised groups frequently criticise top-down policies, especially when these policies are experienced as diminishing their agency and insights, resulting in further distrust of the authorities. **Marginalised groups also find the few existing consultation and collaboration mechanisms merely procedural**, rather than having any concrete and substantial impact.

***Example:** In Türkiye, where wildfires are increasing, a policy regulating civic participation in fire intervention was changed to accommodate volunteers into the existing mechanisms. However, this policy change downgraded the local forest villagers' role in fire prevention and intervention. Feeling that their efforts were not recognised as valuable, the forest villagers started experiencing friction with the authorities, such as not showing willingness to support the fire intervention teams, or demanding more recruitment possibilities for the villagers in the firefighting teams.*

***Example:** In Norway's green energy transition, authorities carried out consultation sessions. However, disadvantaged groups perceived them as merely performative rather than genuine, as authorities seemed to not engage with the community's input. This led to frustration and a sense of neglect in the community.*

- Resistance is particularly common against sustainable transportation policies. Modal shift policies aim to benefit all, **yet the measures implemented tend to disproportionately affect marginalised communities** in the areas that lack efficient public transport. As a result, such measures tend to be seen as top-down and disruptive by these communities.

***Example:** In Italy, policies restricting private car use by creating Green Belt/Low Emission Zones have sparked protests in a disadvantaged neighbourhood in Rome. Allowing only low-emission vehicles in certain areas and imposing fines on others leaves marginalised groups in a challenging conundrum: an overcrowded and unreliable public transport system, which increases the dependence of marginalised residents on private transportation.*

***Example:** In Norway, removing parking spaces for new bike lanes has raised concerns for those with physical or mental health challenges, fearing it would disrupt their routines, as they often rely on personal vehicles.*

- ACCTING’s gender+ perspective ensured a concerted attention to gendered norms, ideals and stereotypes, which have been found to underpin passive forms of resistance – such as avoidance, hesitance, and nonengagement (Stewart et al., 2021). Yet, **sustainability transitions often fail to consider existing gender norms that affect and constrain women and LGBTQI+ people’s lives**, leading to avoidance without overt confrontation.

***Example:** In Italy, women especially those with caregiving responsibilities and migrant women with larger families, face challenges in transitioning to cycling. Their resistance is not to the policies per se but related to the burdens of care work and safety concerns. Many women also report fears of harassment and inappropriate comments as reasons for their reluctance to cycle.*

- ACCTING research identifies **resistance caused by the seemingly incompatible differences between modern governance mechanisms and the nomadic, indigenous, pastoralist and other groups living in/with nature**. Despite the increasing relevance of these groups for sustainable transition and transformation, authorities resist considering new perspectives brought by such groups and their lifestyles, dismissing them as “traditional”, “primitive,” or “anti-modern”. Integrating equity and equality concerns into policy planning requires a thorough review of existing systems, and more radical interventions towards sustainability, when necessary.

Recommendations

The recommendations below are directed towards policymakers. They highlight the importance of acknowledging the perspectives of marginalised groups, learning from their inspiring experiences and practices of resistance, resilience and sustainability, and understanding them as sources and agents of change for generating better policy.

Acknowledging and understanding resistance

1. **Policymakers need to acknowledge and understand resistance within its unique context.** This involves being open to new notions, sites and agents of resistance, while engaging with and avoiding stereotypical and stagnant views of resistant communities. It is also important to be perceptive to the cases of resistance in different parts of Europe i.e., both the North and the South.
2. Policymakers can explore the vulnerabilities and the positions of the resisting actors; use their insights to map **power** relationships in a certain context; and aim to understand the complex **agencies** of disadvantaged groups. While resisting groups can rally behind a common agenda, existing power relations within groups might determine the terms and directions of the resistance, leading to silencing of more complex and intersectional positions within the resistance. Furthermore, resistance can emerge from perceived, experienced, or expected vulnerabilities; the varieties

in the context of resistance can **illuminate the roots of resistance**. Policymakers can collaborate with researchers and civil society organisations to unravel these complexities of resistance.

Engaging with resistance

3. Policymakers can approach resistance as a call for ‘better’ platforms to enhance dialogue and policy co-design. Actors can resist the existing participatory mechanisms, finding them exclusive to privileged actors, disagreeing with the general course of action, or seeing them being implemented only for box-ticking purposes. **Policymakers can establish permanent platforms for dialogue and policy co-design between stakeholders and ensure their inclusivity and sustainability.** To avoid “top-downness” in such platforms, it is important to identify the most resistant civil society actors and communities, involving and/or engaging them in the process.
4. **Policymakers can employ various tools for facilitation, conflict resolution, and dialogue-building to navigate those transition processes being slowed down by resistance, and to ensure the voluntary inclusion of marginalised groups.** Stakeholders can bring in facilitator expertise to implement methods, such as deep democracy, indigenous method of circle process, participatory action, nonviolent communication and many others, and standardise diverse engagement mechanisms, such as local hearing groups, to ensure the inclusion of resisting marginalised groups. When the process encounters obstacles or stagnation, it is crucial to remain patient, flexible, and open to innovative solutions. By viewing tensions as opportunities for untapped potential and valuable insights, policymakers can foster mutual transformation and growth.
5. **Policymakers can engage with resisting marginalised communities and people by leveraging their networks, resources, and wisdom, thereby amplifying their role as agents of change.** Disadvantaged communities often possess valuable social, cultural, and political networks, along with strong solidarity and safety nets. To tap into these resources, policymakers can commit to long-term engagement with the communities, including multiple site visits, paying specific attention to gender+ dynamics and ensuring visits include women’s spaces. It is important to adapt to the communities’ schedules and conditions, to foster effective collaboration.
6. **Policy can channel resistance into a path for community empowerment.** Resistance is sometimes based on unequal access to information, knowledge and confidence to navigate new situations. When policymakers, researchers, and civil society organisations run projects based on community empowerment, capacity-building, or community resilience, these projects become potential sites for engaging with resistance.
7. **Policymakers can also learn from the disadvantaged groups who do not resist and ask: whose voice is missing?** Policies can always be improved. While it is easy to engage with the most vocal groups, other communities who suffer the consequences may remain unheard. To reach these groups, policymakers can deploy targeted strategies, such as consulting associations representing

marginalised groups early in the policy development process — even if these groups are not directly related to the policy’s environmental focus, such as migrant associations.

Transforming resistance

8. Policymakers can identify hotspots, where sustainability transitions and transformations are likely to lead to tensions between social and environmental concerns. Pre-existing axes of inequality often shape vulnerability and disadvantage. Insights gained from resistance can **contribute to long-term solutions to complex matters such as human rights and social equity, cultural heritage protection, and safety from natural hazards**. By fostering alliances between civil society organisations and bottom-up experiences, policymakers can strengthen different causes.

Better Stories

In ACCTING, we use inspiring bottom-up initiatives as ‘*better stories*’, a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis¹⁷ to refer to promising practices that can instil ideas for how to advance individual and collective behavioural change as envisioned by the Green Deal. We have identified potential platforms or spaces for dialogue, co-creation, and collaboration with/in communities enacted by both individuals and collectives. Below we put forward examples from ACCTING’s research on the importance of the presence of community networks to identify and engage resistance.

- In **Italy**, the representatives from the Civil Protection Agency worked with a network of “cultural mediators” who would know the locations of the vulnerable individuals and facilitate connections with them during a disaster situation. Thanks to these mediators, the Agency drew a rough map of the vulnerabilities in the area, which was integrated into disaster intervention plans.
- In **Hungary**, following a mayor’s failed compensation practices after a flood, civil forums were organised to articulate collective resentment. These platforms brought together different experiences of floods and made them visible, which eventually supported improvements in the management of floods.
- By contrast, also in **Hungary**, some local platforms established for biodiversity conservation initiatives lacked community-based decision-making mechanisms. This discouraged some local people’s active engagement as they were sceptical about how decisions were taken in these platforms. Yet, when residents, farmers, and state agencies united, they started creating a sense of community, made new knowledge being accounted for in decisions, and sceptical individuals eventually came to appreciate these platforms.

¹⁷ [Georgis, D. \(2013\). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.](#)

- In **Türkiye**, residents of the Ahmetler village located in a remote mountain forest in the Mediterranean, resisted orders to evacuate due to a growing forest fire. The predominantly older, female villagers knew specific ways in which they could support the fire intervention efforts. A receptive forest engineer who arrived at the site and recognised the villagers' geographical understanding, permitted them to help in the fire response -- and this eventually played a crucial role in stopping the spread of the fire.
- In **Portugal** the CICLOPES¹⁸ initiative tackles resistance to sustainable mobility by tackling financial barriers, lack of skills, and low confidence - commons sources of such resistance. It does so through a community-centred approach that fosters inclusivity, empowerment, and skills development in disadvantaged communities. The initiative offers free bike rentals, making cycling a viable option, and it also reduces resistance by offering training, equipping participants with the skills and confidence to ride safely.
- In **Austria**, refugees in the *Garten der Begegnung*¹⁹ faced a cultural disconnect with the food provided in asylum centres, which did not align with their dietary habits or preferences. In response, they sought alternative ways to access and produce familiar foods, turning to community gardens to grow traditional vegetables that were unavailable in local markets.
- In **Türkiye**, the Izmir Municipality's policy of opening urban gardens in a historically neglected and disadvantaged neighbourhood was met with hesitation and resistance, largely by the migrants and refugee inhabitants. However, the municipal staff organised community gardening and gender-awareness activities, child-care facilities, and long-term community engagements for the women and children of the neighbourhood. This resulted in the women supporting the gardens and expressing a sense of empowerment.

Relevant Green Deal policy areas

The recommendations are linked to all Green Deal policy areas as they are concerned with the resistance to the policies.

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Resisting narrow vision of public interest

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Summary

The aim of this document is to provide policy recommendations to reframe and democratise the concept of "public interest". While often invoked in policy and decision-making, the term is politically charged and remains vague. This ambiguity can prevent communities from engaging in meaningful discussions about their collective priorities and rights. Policymakers, institutions and communities must shift focus from imposing top-down definitions of public interest to foster inclusive, transparent processes that enable diverse voices to define and pursue shared goals. This document provides recommendations to help communities and policymakers foster a collective vision of public interest that is inclusive, dynamic, and responsive to societal needs. By **empowering communities, activist groups, NGOs, media, and academia** to reclaim and reshape public interest, this approach supports the Green Deal's vision that "citizens are, and should remain, a driving force of the transition" towards sustainability (EC, 2019, p. 22).

Introduction

The concept of "public interest" lies at the heart of policy making and governance, yet it remains contested and ambiguous. While often used to justify decisions, its lack of clarity obscures the processes and power dynamics involved in defining what constitutes the public good. This **ambiguity not only risks marginalising certain voices but also discourages meaningful community engagement in shaping collective priorities and rights.**

At its core, public interest is not a static or universal concept; it is inherently political, fluid and shaped by competing values, needs, and perspectives. How it is defined, by whom, and in whose favour, are critical questions that influence its legitimacy and impact. Top-down definitions of public interest can perpetuate inequalities, prioritise dominant groups, and silence dissenting voices. In contrast, **a democratic, inclusive approach to defining public interest can empower communities, foster trust and build societies that are more just and sustainable.**

This factsheet calls for a shift from authoritative definitions to inclusive dialogues and understandings that reflect diverse voices and shared goals. We encourage policymakers and communities to critically examine the *processes* of defining public interest, the *actors* involved, and its implications for their own work:

- What are the dynamics between individual rights and collective needs?
- How do competing interests, such as those of rural versus urban populations, shape our understanding of public good?
- And how can these discussions be made more inclusive and transparent?

Ultimately, redefining public interest is about reshaping the processes that underpin decision-making and ensuring that these processes reflect the values of equity, sustainability, and democracy.

Findings from ACCTING

Key insights from the ACCTING research for policymakers and communities:

- "Public interest" often excludes marginalised voices and reflects the perspective of dominant groups. It is also the other way around; when tensions arise between the communities and authorities, what the public interest is in that situation is usually clear and thereby needs to be clarified through regular meetings.

Example: *In Portugal, the municipal policies of disaster risk management in the greater Lisbon area require urban transformation projects and resettlement in one of the most disadvantaged neighbourhoods, populated predominantly by the migrants. The frequent floods and heat waves have created serious life hazards, however the communities resist moving due to many factors. They lack adequate knowledge about the resettlement sites, fear dissipation of their communities which provide a social safety net and believe that they can adapt to the disasters in their given location. In this situation while public interest is defined as a general societal resilience against disasters, the vulnerable groups do not see its implementation into their unique conditions.*

- Authorities frequently use the term to avoid transparency and suppress dissent.

Example: *In a mid-sized city in Sweden, a new transport system that prioritises bus traffic over car traffic on the city's main thoroughfare caused considerable protests. The policymakers behind the project argued that this system was in the public's interest, but that the public does not always understand what is in their best interest. As they reasoned, the public does not have the knowledge required to predict what transport needs the city will have in ten years. The expert knowledge of the traffic planning department trumped other knowledge claims and public consultation was actively avoided as it was seen as mainly a hindrance to achieve a necessary transition. Also clear from this case was that the public was defined as the "broad masses", and the impact on marginalised group was given limited attention.*

- Bottom-up and grassroots initiatives can crucially contribute to redefining public interest in more inclusive and democratic ways, as reflected through ACCTING's research (see the *better stories* below).

Recommendations

The recommendations below are primarily directed towards i) civil society organisations, ii) policy makers and a set of recommendations here are directed towards iii) both actors.

I: Scrutinising top-down public interest

Authorities often weaponise the term “public interest” to shut down critiques of new or unpopular policies. Civil society actors need to:

1. **Highlight misuse:** Document and publicise cases where “public interest” is used to suppress critique, justify unpopular policies or bypass the process of public participation in decision making.
2. **Demand accountability:** Advocate for transparency and accountability in decision-making processes to expose how authorities invoke “public interest” in their policies on contested areas of public policy.
3. **Illustrate consequences:** Use examples to show how narrow or exclusive definitions of public interest can be detrimental towards marginalised and vulnerable communities and to democracy.

II: Empowering bottom-up definitions of public interest

Communities should be encouraged to reclaim and redefine “public interest.” Policymakers can support this by:

4. **Amplifying grassroots efforts:** Share successful cases of initiatives that reflect community-driven definitions of public interest, such as the deliberative democracy practices in Canada, Agenda 21, and the e5-Gemeinde (*energieeffiziente Gemeinden*²⁰ “energy efficient communities”). Also highlight the existence of initiatives such as the new Competence Centre on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy in the EU.
5. **Establishing solidarity networks:** Create platforms for grassroots initiatives, civil society organisations, and other publics to organise discussions about common interests and how to pursue them within existing mechanisms. This can be done by organising forums, workshops, and platforms for inclusive discussions about public interest.
6. **Providing tools and metrics:** Promote the development of impact criteria and tools to assess the impact and inclusivity of initiatives promoting public interest.
7. **Transforming governance:** Establish multi-sector networks across civil society and academia to explore paths to transform the existing governance mechanisms towards more transparency and accountability.

²⁰ <https://www.e5-gemeinden.at/english/en/e5-programme>

III: Pluralising singular concepts (publics, interests, democracies)

The meaning of the term "public", "interest" and "democracy" must be reimagined as dynamic, diverse and inclusive. Policymakers and communities can support this by:

8. **Raising awareness:** Launch public campaigns to highlight the need for a shift to inclusive vision-building and evolving definitions of public interest tied to changing and place-based societal contexts.
9. **Establishing feedback loops:** Regularly evaluate how public interest is defined and implemented, ensuring its efficiency, inclusivity, and alignment with democratic values.
10. **Promoting pluralism:** Recognise that public interest may differ across urban and rural areas, majority and minority groups, and other social divides. Policies should reflect these diverse perspectives.

Better Stories

In ACCTING we use '*better stories*', a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis²¹, to refer to promising practices that identify how a given societal situation can be ameliorated to improve existing practices.

Akbelen Forest Solidarity²² collective in Türkiye: an environmental struggle to protect forests threatened by coal mining redefined public interest based on the rights of people to a healthy environment and to continue to make a sustainable living. This included the right of future generations to inherit an undisturbed and unpolluted environment. This clashed with the state's definition of public interest, which was based on the energy needs of industry and general use and could not prevent the forest from being destroyed. This case provides alternative perspectives on public interest that can also be relevant for other environmental struggles. Even though the forest was eventually destroyed and the mining project expanded, this struggle strengthened the case for environmental rights as a principle for public interest. The Akbelen collective continues its forest watch near to the destroyed forest, to continue documenting the environmental harm produced by the mine and provide support to other local anti-mining forest defence movements across the country.

Echoversity²³ is a pilot project carried out by the Ecomuseum in Greece. In the project, the civil society organisers closely worked with the transhumance communities, scientists, and ordinary citizens to create sound maps of the transhumance routes. The project was born out of the goal to support the transhumance communities, whose ecological and traditional

²¹Georgis, D. (2013). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.

²²<https://ikizkoydireniyor.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/AKBELEN-FOREST INFO NOTE OCTOBER-2023 s.pdf>

²³<https://ecomuseumzaqori.gr/en/echoversity/>

knowledge have historically been unacknowledged through sustainable tourism while also increasing public engagement with and knowledge of natural areas. The public engagement models varied from increased interactions between environmental scientists and citizens to festivals around local cultures. The project showcased a participatory model of forging a common agenda across different public sectors around the ultimate goal of sustainability and environmental protection.

Relevant Green Deal policy areas

As a cross-cutting theme that is concerned with the processes, actors, and the impact of policies designed according to public interest, this factsheet is relevant to all Green Deal policy areas. The Green Deal has several policies that emphasises collective well-being, sustainability and equitable resource distribution. The following policy areas are aligned with the concept of public interest:

- Green city accord
- EU water framework directive
- Just transition mechanism
- Sustainable and smart mobility strategy
- Circular economy action plan
- Zero pollution action plan
- Clean energy for all.

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Promoting policy innovations that promote commons

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Summary

ACCTING's research activities show the positive impact commons can have on a just transition. Commons are inclusive, and their positive impact on marginalised populations is real. Promoting both existing and new commons (i.e., those to be created), is therefore a sensible investment for policymakers who want the transition to be inclusive. This factsheet presents examples of innovative policies that promote and support the commons. Such examples are all too rare today, and the purpose of the factsheet is thus to draw attention to their benefits and to inspire policymakers to support commons. Existing recommendations for policymakers on the importance of commons and the need to support them are also highlighted, with ACCTING research confirming their pertinence and potential for reaching vulnerable and marginalised people.

Introduction

Commons are vital for fostering social harmony, environmental sustainability and economic resilience. Nonetheless, they are increasingly under pressure from privatisation, stress due to overuse, and inadequate governance frameworks. The policy landscape often lags in addressing the governance of commons. Current approaches to address this issue frequently prioritise state-centred or market-driven frameworks. This situation risks undermining the logic of self-organisation, cooperation and inclusion – key factors in determining the effectiveness of commons in managing resources for the benefit of both communities and the environment. In the current context of rising inequalities, environmental degradation and social division, the need for policy innovations to promote the commons and processes of commoning are even more significant. This calls for the kind of multidisciplinary and participatory approach undertaken by ACCTING – one that draws on the lived experiences of communities, integrates diverse knowledge systems through its co-creation work, and at the same time roots itself in the EU's broader objectives of social justice and environmental sustainability.

Findings from ACCTING

While ACCTING's research did not directly and consistently address questions pertaining to commons, it nevertheless identified the important role commons play in addressing the needs of different target groups (including the most vulnerable) and their potential contribution to a just transition. The concept of commons encompasses both collective resources – including natural resources such as ecosystems, and public resources like energy or public space, and the form of collective ownership, organising and governance of these resources. Findings from across ACCTING's thematic research lines illustrate how commons have played a role in processes of behavioural change towards sustainability.

- In terms of **disaster prevention and recovery**, the management of commons has been shown to play an important role. Whether in cooperation with the (local) authorities or not, communities have come together and used their specialised knowledge to protect and safeguard natural areas in their environment, engaging in disaster prevention, mitigation and recovery efforts when confronted with wildfires, flooding or other similar events. This local caretaking of commons by communities often goes against prevailing neoliberal logics, with authorities ignorant or neglectful of the crucial work performed by residents to counter disasters.
- The impulse to safeguard commons and their **biodiversity** is visible in cases where local communities resist projects that impact their natural surroundings. The research found that biodiversity protection and habitat conservation is emphasised by those living near natural parks or other valued natural areas. Through education and training, these communities aim to ensure that environmentally beneficial practices are promoted and that behaviours are changed, especially among younger generations. Moreover, cultural traditions and practices related to nature were often found to be important in small communities to educate people about how to behave in and with nature. These values and skills support an understanding of the benefits of natural commons and of how to care for them.
- As for **energy consumption and production**, energy community schemes have been highlighted as a form of energy commons with the potential to reduce energy poverty and vulnerability in both urban and rural areas. Motivations to change behaviour and acquire the necessary competences for managing community-owned sustainable energy resources can come from a variety of sources, including the pride that people can feel from participating in energy communities, the need to save on energy costs, and any financial incentives offered by the authorities (i.e., to install photovoltaic systems). By leveraging these motivations, processes of energy commoning can be stimulated.
- In the case of **sustainable food**, ACCTING has observed various initiatives and organisations striving to improve the availability of sustainable food and promoting the common-adjacent concepts of edible schools and edible cities. Making food cultivation and preparation more accessible for a multitude of societal groups was a recurring phenomenon for the studied initiatives. By engaging in practices like introducing people to permaculture practices, reusing food waste in cooking

activities, and promoting social inclusion through participatory activities, food commons can help promote more sustainable production and consumption behaviours.

- Another area where commoning can motivate behavioural change is in the field of **sustainable mobility**. Mobile commons, where diverse mobility means are shared (as opposed to privately-owned transport means) and co-exist in harmony, promote the shared use of public spaces.

Recommendations

The aim here is to highlight relevant pre-existing recommendations, from individuals and organisations outside of ACCTING to policymakers who have been active in promoting the commons. The intention is to explore the impact of commons and the need for policy initiatives to support them. This factsheet intends to emphasise that the current neoliberal system often hinders participation in civic life; by perpetuating economic inequalities and social barriers, limiting access to resources, education, and platforms needed for meaningful engagement in decision-making and reform processes. In this section we further accentuate the following recommendations, as the ACCTING research has underlined their relevance and importance. They are relevant for policymakers at various levels, including the local, national and European levels.

- **Establish laws that officially recognise and support commons governance models** alongside public and private models of ownership. This framework should be able to define the rights, responsibilities, and diverse governance mechanisms for communities managing shared resources.
- **Promote the transformation of unoccupied or underutilised urban spaces into shared green commons through incentives to stimulate the reclamation of these spaces by local communities.** At the same time, mandate participatory urban planning processes to involve citizens in the co-creation of green commons.
- **Adopt policies that encourage public-civic partnerships for urban commons**, so that grassroots initiatives that aim to create or renew commons can rely on institutional support when needed and can play a role in urban governance mechanisms to defend their interests. One possible way for (local) policymakers to enable this is to set up funding programmes that support urban commons projects. At the EU level, funding can also be proactively allocated to small-scale community projects (i.e., not carried out by large consortia) through existing programmes like the European Regional Development Fund, the Cohesion Fund, the LIFE programme and the Horizon programme (Bloemen & Hammerstein, 2017). This would have implications for the current design of these programmes: the expanded use of mechanisms like FSTP (Financial Support for Third Parties) could be a way forward to reach small-scale community projects.

- **Support energy commons at the EU level** by dedicating significant parts of the EU energy budget to community-led renewable energy projects (and the infrastructure that this requires). As highlighted in Hammerstein & Bloemen (2016), EU energy policy can do more to facilitate and promote community-controlled and community-produced renewable energy by having EU funding programmes prioritise commons-based energy production, by enshrining the right to sell electricity to the grid, and by providing financial risk facilities for community energy projects.
- **Transition from the EU's current common agricultural policy to a common food policy**, to de-commodify food and food production and move to a sustainable, community-supported food system. As previously advocated by Vivero-Pol (2019) and IPES Food, a Common Food Policy (CFP) would help harmonise EU policies on food, agriculture, climate, environment, trade, health, and social issues, which are currently – in some cases – working towards contradictory ends. The CFP would enable and support commons-based initiatives like collective food buying groups and community-supported agriculture. These emphasise fairness and environmental sustainability, while reducing the disproportionate influence of large food industry corporations over agriculture and food policy.

Better Stories

Policy initiatives that promote commons in the context of climate change and the necessary transition are all too rare. In this section, we mention some innovative initiatives from authorities at different levels (from local to EU), that show the way forward.

- Within its energy policy, the EU has long recognised the power of collective, democratic forms of organising the ownership and governance of resources. The 2019, **Clean Energy for All Europeans Package**²⁴, including the Renewable Energy Directive (REDII) and Internal Energy Market Directive (IEMD), recognises and supports citizen and renewable energy communities as a key contributor to the energy transition. These policies aim to facilitate market access and energy sharing for small-scale, citizen-led renewable energy initiatives. They also require Member States to create an enabling framework to support these communities, for instance in their development of National Energy and Climate Plans. In their transposition into national policies, such as the German Erneuerbare Energien Gesetz (EEG), enabling policies include the legal recognition of energy communities, financial incentives, and special auctioning permissions for small-scale projects to reduce competitive pressures vis-a-vis larger commercial players. While the implementation is still patchy and partly insufficient to foster truly inclusive energy commons, there are today over 9000 energy communities in the EU, involving more than 1.5 million citizens. As such, the EU's energy policy can be regarded as a blueprint to promote

²⁴ https://wayback.archiveit.org/12090/20241209144917/https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-strategy/clean-energy-all-europeans-package_en

commons-based forms of organisation in other Green Deal priority areas, such as food and agriculture, climate action and emerging policy priorities, like housing.

- The “third place” is a concept introduced by sociologist Ray Oldenburg (1989) that refers to the space that is neither the home nor the place of work. This is a neutral ground where many social interactions take place. This concept has been interpreted in very diverse ways. France is a country where the concept has been embraced by civil society under the name “tiers-lieu” with a focus on the spatial aspect and social cohesion. The State has developed support mechanisms to strengthen these third places with the creation of hundreds of spaces. This is done through the ANCT (the national agency for “coherence of territories”). An [evaluation](#) of this approach is available.
- The **City as a Commons**²⁵ project started in 2011 in Bologna with the support from *Fondazione del Monte di Bologna e Ravenna* and the city of Bologna. This led to new regulation on collaboration between citizens and the city for the care and regeneration of urban commons in the city. This is now known as the Bologna Regulation, a 30-page regulatory framework delineating the ways local authorities, citizens, communities, SMEs, nonprofits and other institutions can co-manage public and private assets. The regulation calls for new frameworks and tools for collaborative urban/local governance. Cities like Ghent and Madrid have tailored the regulation to their circumstances with the aim of establishing a cooperative relationship between the city and its citizens for the management of urban commons.
- The **Tempelhofer Feld**²⁶ is a former airfield of the Tempelhof Airport. It is now used as a park and leisure area, covering around 304 hectares. Since 2010, it has been open to the public for recreational and leisure use, offering various civic projects such as an intercultural education centre, a community garden, a talent school, a high ropes arena, mini art golf, a district garden and more. In a referendum in 2014, the people of Berlin voted against building on the edges of the site and in favour of preserving Tempelhofer Feld in its current state. As a result, the "Law for the Preservation of Tempelhofer Feld" (ThFG) came into force in June 2014, which defines the purpose of the area's protection and the preservation goals. Tempelhofer Feld is a case of success as it is a commons where a referendum was held, and more than 60 percent of the Berliners supported the idea of banning construction on the former airfield. And the urban garden initiative situated in Tempelhofer Feld reflects the community's use of a common pool of resources. At the same time, a failure as the airfield is now managed in a top- down exclusive manner by the city government.
- Through the **Kleineschholz project**, the City of Freiburg is supporting housing commons in its urban developments. The municipality's bidding process for eleven building permits is open exclusively to common good, oriented actors and follows criteria of affordability, inclusivity and sustainability. It thus excludes profit-driven investors in favour of cooperative and public-led social housing. So far, three

²⁵ <https://www.shareable.net/how-bologna-is-regenerating-the-urban-commons/>

²⁶ <https://kleineschholz-syndikat.org/#mietshaeuser-syndikat>

housing cooperatives organised under the *Mietshäusersyndikat* (apartment-house syndicate) model have been approved. This model grants a veto right on property sales and privatisation to the Syndikat, thus removing properties from speculative markets to ensure long-term affordability and community-ownership. The resulting self-organised housing projects feature a strong focus on inclusivity, for example, by focusing on mutual care for elderly residents in Birnbaum project and educational space for disadvantaged girls in Elinor-Ostrom Siedlungsprojekt 1 (EOS1). Supported by municipal subsidies tied to rent caps, the Kleineschholz project demonstrates how public-cooperative collaborations can create sustainable housing solutions.

- Amsterdam's **Incubator for the Community Economy**²⁷ seeks to support grassroots initiatives and foster a democratic, localised economy. A coalition of civil society organisations, with municipal support, launched the incubator to promote socio-economic change, in line with the vision of the [Donut Economy](#). The incubator supports initiatives that democratise ownership and governance, emphasise social value and ecological regeneration, and create tangible benefits for local communities. Inspired by the principles of commons, the incubator supports diverse models such as cooperatives. Such initiatives often face obstacles like rigid institutional frameworks and funding challenges. The incubator bridges these gaps through funding support, knowledge-sharing, and network-building.

Relevant Green Deal policy areas

The Green Deal aims to tackle multi-dimensional sustainability challenges in a fair, inclusive and collaborative manner. The commons are a promising vehicle to implement this ambition. Even though many Green Deal policies emphasise sustainability, inclusivity and participation, they generally lack explicit regulatory and sufficient financial support for the commons and processes of commoning. Some policies in which innovative mechanisms to support the commons could be mainstreamed include:

1. Farm to fork strategy
2. EU biodiversity strategy for 2030.
3. Circular economy action plan
4. Clean energy for all Europeans package
5. EU-climate adaptation strategy
6. EU-forest strategy for 2030
7. EU water framework directive and marine strategy framework directive
8. Green city accord initiative
9. New European Bauhaus.

²⁷ <https://www.commonsnetwork.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Verkenning-Incubator-Gemeenschapseconomie-Commons-Network-2022.pdf>

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Public Civil Society Partnerships for behavioural change

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Summary

Local authorities often lack the resources and capacity to address complex societal challenges, particularly those related to the Green Deal, while bottom-up community initiatives face barriers including poor communication with local governments and bureaucratic hurdles. These challenges hinder collaborative efforts that could leverage both local government resources and community-driven passion to tackle climate change and support vulnerable populations. The ACCTING project has demonstrated the benefits of partnerships between local governments and civil society organisations (CSOs) in addressing major societal challenges such as climate change. Successful partnerships should be systematic and strategic and be based on a shared vision of equity, transparency, and community engagement, with clear communication, flexibility, and a focus on sustainability. These strategic partnerships can help bridge the gap between local governments and CSOs, ultimately contributing to the Green Deal's broader goals by fostering systemic change and community involvement.

Introduction

Local authorities often lack the necessary knowledge and skills, funds (funding shortages are endemic in many smaller communities), and human resources to tackle complex societal challenges, especially those addressed by the Green Deal and researched through the ACCTING project.

At the same time, bottom-up initiatives that involve civil society and community level organisations often face hurdles in their activities due to lack of communication with local authorities and what can, at times, be perceived as “unnecessary and/or self-promoting” bureaucracy. Thus, bottom-up initiatives struggle to be fully implemented as they face regulatory hurdles on top of the usual internal resource constraints. Lack of communication and coordination between civil society and local government creates barriers and misses a significant opportunity: that of bringing together the embedded knowledge, skills, and passion of the community with the tools and resources of the local government, in order to induce behavioural change and tackle the challenges that climate change presents, especially for vulnerable and marginalised populations.

Although CSOs and local governments do often cooperate to tackle emergencies or other situations as they arise, the lack of *systematic* engagement misses the opportunity for more coordinated and targeted interventions and initiatives. The ACCTING project, through its [research](#) and [pilot actions](#), has highlighted the positive effects that coordination and cooperation between bottom-up initiatives and local governments can have in terms of recognising the areas of potential improvement, advocating for change, and working together systemically to tackle major societal challenges

Findings from ACCTING

The following are experiences from the Pilot Actions that were supported by ACCTING. More about the Pilot Actions can be found on the ACCTING website [here](#).

Dock, an NGO in Messinia, Peloponnese, Greece cooperated with local authorities and engaged mountain communities to co-create a scenario for handling a wildfire disaster using a bottom-up approach, to inform and trigger behavioural change. Through a participatory design process, the project set up digital platforms to facilitate discussion on the ethical dimension of disaster management, and conducted hands-on scenarios to form a coordinated community-based response to disaster.

Kokoza, an NGO in Prague, Czech Republic, engaged local communities, municipalities and private developers in a collaboration regarding community gardens in the Czech Republic, resulting in agreements to include community gardens in urban planning, with a memorandum of understanding facilitating green spaces in new residential projects.

Young Researchers of Serbia (YRS), an NGO in Belgrade, developed a methodology that can support informal groups at the local level. It created a platform that is currently used by local and national authorities, as well as private donors, to streamline support to grassroots initiatives at a local level. This is important as it addresses a major hurdle: individuals and informal groups cannot be supported or held accountable for financial spending through projects and donations.

Mamagea, an NGO in Thessaloniki, Greece cooperated with the municipality of Thessaloniki to create a local action plan for sustainable food systems. This resulted in the creation of the Thessaloniki Food Council, charged with promoting healthy, environmentally sustainable food to local schools. Food is framed as a common good (instead of a commodity), which can lead to policies, practices and frameworks that achieve social justice across different socio-economic groups. The work of the pilot project facilitated the engagement of municipal employees, which typically is something that happens top-down, needs official permission and can lead to delays and disengagement.

Recommendations

Community engagement and interpersonal relationships can inspire individual awareness and knowledge. Conversely, a lack of social ties or appreciation, social resistance, and norms that continue to encourage negative environmental behaviour, make change a lonely and difficult process (ACCTING's own extensive research indicates that 'community belonging' is a key enabler of pro-environmental behaviour change). Mobilising and partnering local government with community-based initiatives and CSOs in a systematic and strategic way provides a basis to address these issues. In parallel, this can benefit both civil society organisations (ensuring more sustainable and systemic impact of their activities), and local authorities (boosting the resources and knowledge available to them and tackling those issues that are a priority for their communities). Considering the mutual benefit both actors can have, recommendations below suggest successful strategic partnerships between CSOs and local governments. This can serve as a springboard for citizen engagement and a multiplier of efforts to address major societal challenges. Essential elements of a successful, resilient, and sustainable partnership include:

1. The vision

Local authorities and CSOs engage in a dynamic and systematic dialogue to co-create a common vision, based on the principles of equity, justice, transparency and caring for the most vulnerable and marginalised. This can connect climate change (a global phenomenon) with local problems / situations (floods, loss of biodiversity, droughts) and bring together community knowledge with local resources in the search for solutions. The vision of the Partnership needs to:

- Define, respect, and protect the civic space.
- Be strategic: aim at mobilising and incentivising citizens to adopt behaviour and practices that make a positive contribution to tackling climate change.
- Be systematic: define mechanisms for continuous consultation and participation; continuously monitor challenges and opportunities and coordinate resources.
- Motivate citizens and activists to become ambassadors of change.
- Focus on building trust and confidence over the longer term. Local authorities should not hide behind bureaucracy but should strive to make the system work for the benefit of communities and CCOs that they partner with.

2. The approach

Local authorities recognising the need to systematically and strategically engage with civil society need to:

- Create a space and a platform to pool resources. This needs to have defined mechanisms for recognising needs and available skills and resources and offer a simple way to mobilise public and civic society capacities.
- Have clear lines of communication, assigning contact persons and ensuring that they are developing an ongoing relationship with civil society.
- Recognise widespread lack of facilitation and co-creation know-how within city administrations, investing in developing the skills and capacity needed to engage with and support communities and CSOs. This can include support in engagement and participation of citizens, and innovation at a governance level.
- Reward city officials for being brave enough to think outside the box and acting creatively and even bringing in external facilitation support where possible or necessary.
- Avoid overlapping work by ensuring an open dialogue and being transparent about needs and resources available.
- Plan but be flexible to tackle unforeseen challenges.
- Facilitate advocacy for policy change at higher levels by demonstrating the efficiency of locally developed solutions and initiatives.
- Build trust by treating CSOs and citizens as ambassadors of change. As far as possible, seek to minimise a perception of focus on rules, regulations and other bureaucratic hurdles, in favour of genuine support for substantive issues. This should create space for people to volunteer for practical activities that improve their community in a tangible way, since people rarely volunteer for administrative or bureaucratic activities.
- Foster social connections and support networks through community-building initiatives that prioritise environmental awareness and environmentally friendly practices.
- Promote and normalise environmentally friendly behaviours and climate change adaptation through positive messaging and role models, including politicians themselves acting in line with the Green Deal ambitions.

CSOs partnering with local authorities need to:

- Be transparent and open about their goals and capacity.
- Be ready to share skills and resources and cooperate in a way that has multiplying effects.
- Be proactive in bringing forward concerns and potential barriers.

- Be professional in contacting public authorities and other CSOs, with clear communication of goals and capacities, clear reporting, and clearly defined contact persons.

3. The tools

Tackling challenges associated with climate change and co-creating appropriate solutions requires the use of citizen engagement tools. The public – civil society partnership can be enhanced by:

- Engaging in meaningful dialogue.
- Using a palette of tools to engage citizens and tap into local knowledge, adapted to local specificities. These may include:
 - co-creation events
 - online consultations
 - citizen assemblies
 - citizen science initiatives
 - representative deliberative processes and
 - running of simulations and pilots.
- Using digital tools (including social media) but not exclusively, so that digitally illiterate citizens (oftentimes belonging to vulnerable groups) are not excluded.
- Making local data available to facilitate open innovation and crowdsourcing.
- Communicating the vision, the process, and the results of initiatives undertaken.
- Involving citizens in the monitoring and evaluation of public decisions, policies, and services.
- Streamlining available funding, supporting the vision in an accountable and transparent way.

Facilitating fundraising from private sector donors (i.e., through CSR). A systematic, community engaged vision for behavioural change can be appealing to private donors.

4. The sustainability of the partnership

The public — civil society partnership needs to move from one-off engagements to a sustainable relationship that nurtures continuous dialogue, openness, reflectiveness, and proactivity. It can strengthen public engagement and ensure inclusion and accessibility by involving CSOs and citizens in policy making decisions and facilitating their sense of agency. It can also raise awareness and facilitate public learning about climate change and the Green Deal and promote volunteerism as an essential element of the civil space at the local level.

Better Stories

In ACCTING, we look for inspiring bottom-up initiatives as ‘*better stories*’, a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis²⁸ to refer to promising practices that can instil ideas for how to advance individual and collective behavioural change as envisioned by the Green Deal. Also, listed below are some relevant cases representing public civil society partnership.

Voluntary system of civil defence of Florence²⁹ Since the terrible floods in 1966, many citizens' organisations and groups have cooperated daily with the municipal civil defence system. It is a free and organised force. It represents an extraordinary resource in terms of skills and operational capacity with more than five thousand organisations across the country.

Gradski vrtovi Sisak (Urban Gardening Sisak) in Croatia³⁰ is a unique concept; ambitious volunteers cleared up construction and heavy industry waste at a site and turned it into an urban community garden in a city with the majority being low-income and elderly people. Sisak City officially became the seventh Croatian city that can boast of the City Gardens project with the full support of the Mayor. The project leader mentioned that the project idea came through observing other cities in Croatia that have successfully transformed neglected land areas into splendid gardens. She said: “We intend to arrange this area in such a way that it will be possible to stay there all day because we plan to install swings and climbing frames for children, arrange a swimming pool and use this area for work and leisure, which will provide a pleasant and fun all-day stay for the whole family”.

Energy Community of Ii in Finland³¹ Over more than a decade, the approximately 10,000 residents of the municipality of Ii have reduced their municipality’s emissions by 80 percent. Ii’s municipal economic development strategy was revised after its previous tech-driven economy fell into crisis. Decision-makers took the important decision to stimulate the economy through sustainable means, as climate efforts were not seen as putting the brakes on business. The success of the reduction was due to the joint efforts of the whole municipality working to reduce carbon emissions. Residents were asked for their ideas and input on the design of green services. The views of different age groups were heard in different ways. Through strategic efforts, renewable energy has become an important sector for the local economy, complementing various other industries (e.g., the rubber, plastics and packaging, construction, fine mechanics, and metal industries).

Soil-to-Soil Biodegradable Waste Management Project – We Make Life Better Environment and Climate Association³² (“Yaşamı İyileştiriyoruz Çevre ve İklim Derneği”) in **Türkiye** was established in 2021, collects biodegradable waste food, consisting of vegetables and fruits, from the marketplaces (bazaars) and transforms them into compost for soil regeneration in agriculture. Disadvantaged women are included in the project by working in the community kitchens/food banks where the usable food left in the marketplace is cooked and distributed. The Association has established partnerships with 52

²⁸ [Georgis, D. \(2013\). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.](#)

²⁹ <https://www.cittametropolitana.fi.it/protezione-civile>.

³⁰ <https://zelenozlato.org/index.php/izgradnja-zajednica-i-inkluzija/9-gradski-vrtovi-sisak>

³¹ <https://ii.fi/kestava-arki>

³² <http://yasamiyilestiriyoruz.org/>

municipalities and several academics in Türkiye. The government authorities do not provide finances but can/do support in another way, such as designating lands that can be used as compost areas and providing the necessary equipment for compost production and distribution.

Below are case studies taken an example demonstrating successful public civil society partnerships:

The **Municipalities in Transition**³³ project includes a great number of further case studies, categorised by country. Many include inspiration for CSO-local government collaboration such as:

Parceria Local de Telheiras (“Telheiras Local Partnership”) is a neighbourhood partnership that brings local organisations, citizens, and local government representatives together to collectively identify local needs and solutions, thereby strengthening local identity and addressing a lack of resources. The project has been running since 2013, and in addition to hosting such community events, has established a website to publicise local events, services and skills, created a volunteer bank, and an institutional training and qualification process.

La Ruche qui dit Oui³⁴ (“**The Beehive that says Yes**”) is an initiative active across numerous European countries that seeks to promote local food producers and shorter supply chains by using a website and app to link would-be consumers to producers in their region. A further aspect is the establishment of a series of “hives” located in different neighbourhoods, which serve as delivery and collection points. Consumers are also able to learn more about the needs and practicalities of these local producers.

Zukunftsstadt Dresden³⁵ (“**Future City Dresden**”) is a municipality-led programme that ran between 2015 and 2022. It used a three-phase approach to incorporate citizen perspectives into urban development processes. Many individual visions for a sustainable city were gathered through workshops (phase I). These were combined into a common vision of the future (Phase II) and finally served as a guide for implementation of real-life projects (phase III).

Relevant Green Deal policy areas

The policy recommendations described above cut across all Policy Areas of the Green Deal as they address issues related to local strategy and planning, infrastructure, regulations, building trust and sharing knowledge and resources which can greatly benefit all aspects of the Green Deal.

³³ <https://municipalitiesintransition.org/about-the-case-studies/case-studies/>

³⁴ <https://laruchequiditoui.fr/fr>

³⁵ <https://www.zukunftsstadt-dresden.de/>

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Commons for all

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Summary

The concept of commons can play a crucial role in driving inclusive behavioural change, aligning with the Green Deal's sustainability and social equity goals. Commons are shared resources managed collectively by a community, governed through self-organised and cooperative institutions to ensure sustainable use and equitable access (Ostrom, 1990). ACCTING's research highlights how community-managed commons, such as urban gardens, energy communities, and shared mobility systems, can foster sustainable behaviours while strengthening social ties and promoting environmental stewardship.

However, our research has revealed that marginalised groups often encounter barriers to accessing and benefiting from commons initiatives. These barriers include i) limited access to resources, ii) insufficient or poorly maintained infrastructure to support commons activities, and iii) entrenched social inequalities, which can limit participation or decision-making opportunities for marginalised population

The findings from ACCTING's research indicate that targeted programmes addressing marginalised groups can overcome these barriers and create opportunities for sustainable participation. Programmes to engage vulnerable families in urban commons were particularly successful.

To maximise the potential of commons, it is essential to form strong partnerships with governments, communities, and NGOs, and invest in pilot projects. At the same time, these collaborations can opt for sustainable funding initiatives and showcase successful examples for wider adoption. By incorporating the commons into public policies, municipalities can enhance environmental, social, and economic resilience, and foster more sustainable and inclusive communities.

Introduction

With the ongoing and rapid pace of urbanisation, cities are at the forefront of complex global challenges, including rising food prices, climate change, environmental degradation, and sustainability concerns. However, the impact of urbanisation is not experienced equally by all. Since urban spaces are not uniform but rather contested environments, they are shaped by power relations, inequalities, and marginalisation (Harvey, 2008). Urban inequalities, shaped by factors like income, race, ethnicity, and gender, disproportionately affect

marginalised groups, especially in the face of climate change, housing crises, and economic instability. Yet, in urban settings, these same challenges can also create opportunities and new ways to address these issues, thereby building stronger, more resilient communities.

Commons, in essence, differ from public spaces, in being citizen-led and having collective management. They run on the principle of a shared sense of responsibility among their users (O'Neil et al., 2021; Federici, 2018). The principles of collective ownership and self-governance are important for marginalised groups because it provides them with collective control over resources and decision-making. As feminists have argued, this form of collective control not only challenges hierarchical and patriarchal structures that often marginalises women's contributions. It also creates spaces where marginalised voices, particularly women and indigenous communities, can resist capitalist exploitation and build a pathway to a more just and equitable society (Federici, 2018). The ACCTING research has focused on urban commons related to food security initiatives involving collective cooking and producing. It has shown how urban food commons, such as collective kitchens and community gardens, can serve as common spaces for collective food production. In addition to collectivising food production and preparation specifically among women, the research also unpacks the crucial role of the commons in empowering the women engaged in these activities and fostering community connections. The lack of such spaces specifically exacerbates the challenge of limited access to healthy and sustainable food for marginalised communities.

In many urban environments, there is a disconnect between people, especially marginalised populations, and nature. Urban spaces, often crowded and industrialised, offer few opportunities for these marginalised groups to engage in sustainable practices that would also contribute to their community's well-being. Commons play an important role in supporting marginalised populations by providing access to shared resources and fostering collective action, which yields social, economic, and environmental benefits. Research has demonstrated that commons enhance food security, create connections with others, provide social integration, and improve individual and communal well-being. Furthermore, commons empower marginalised groups: they encourage participation, collaboration, and decision-making among these groups to advocate for their rights and forge social networks across various advocacy initiatives. Through commons, these groups can become active citizens, engaged in addressing their issues and finding their own solutions.

Findings from ACCTING

Insights from various research lines within ACCTING illustrate how commons-based approaches can stimulate more inclusive transitions towards sustainability.

Sustainable and healthy food

In the field of sustainable food, ACCTING has observed initiatives that promote food commons through practices such as edible gardens and urban farming. **Programmes that make food cultivation and preparation accessible to diverse social groups help foster sustainable food systems.** These initiatives often emphasise community participation and

inclusion, integrating practices like permaculture, reducing food waste, and educating participants on sustainable food production. **Community food commons contribute to changing consumption habits and increasing access to nutritious, locally produced food.**

Biodiversity conservation and environmental protection

Communities living near natural areas (and depend on them for their livelihood) often resist development projects that threaten their environments, **advocating for the protection of local ecosystems**. Indigenous and local communities often demonstrate alternative ways of relating to nature as a source of commons. They regard natural entities as actors of their own right and execute more sustainable natural resources management models. **These models and practices help instil an understanding of the value of commons and the importance of their care**, fostering a collective approach to sustaining biodiversity. These grassroots efforts to manage commons often counter dominant neoliberal policies, which may overlook or neglect the vital role of local communities in environmental stewardship.

Disaster prevention and recovery

The destruction increasingly caused by natural disasters has generally increased public awareness of the natural environment as commons. **This has led to increased participation in civic protection and intervention agencies and in formation of many local disaster intervention initiatives.** One of the pilot projects implemented under ACCTING revealed actions like establishing a cross-sectoral advisory board with all the relevant stakeholders, hands-on collaborative scenario planning exercises, simulation of disaster response drills, setting up both physical and digital platforms to facilitate open community discussions on vulnerabilities, equality, and the ethical dimensions of disaster. These activities show significant benefit in advancing communities' preparedness and resilience in the face of disasters and thereby further protection of commons

Energy communities

ACCTING has provided examples of how community energy projects (from Norway, Denmark, and Italy) can stimulate more inclusive transitions towards sustainability. The research emphasises how crowdfunding and shared ownership create a sense of collective responsibility and encourage participation from individuals who might not have the resources to invest in large-scale renewable energy projects individually. The research has also underscored the importance of overcoming the language barriers and limited digital literacy that often restrict the full participation of vulnerable individuals in energy communities. Language barriers can exclude individuals from accessing information, participating in discussions, and expressing their opinions — ultimately limiting their involvement in decision-making processes.

Recommendations

These recommendations are based on ACCTING's research activity and intended for local authorities, nonetheless, it is relevant for NGOs as some of the recommendations focus on collaborations between these actors.

Leverage urban commons to advance Inclusivity in Sustainability Programmes

Urban commons, such as community gardens, offer a unique opportunity to engage vulnerable populations in sustainability practices. Local authorities and NGOs should collaborate to develop programmes that use these spaces to promote sustainable behaviours, especially among marginalised groups. **By organising hands-on activities, such as gardening, nature walks, and food-sharing initiatives, municipalities can foster behavioural change and help residents, particularly immigrant and low-income families, connect with urban green environments.** These experiences not only highlight the importance of sustainability but also encourage physical activity, community engagement, and a sense of belonging, which are key to developing long-term sustainable habits.

Introduce diverse and inclusive forms of self-governance of commons

Maintaining self-governance of commons requires a collaborative approach that ensures inclusivity and empowers marginalised and vulnerable communities. **Local authorities should prioritise partnerships with NGOs that work closely with these groups, enabling equitable access to urban commons and fostering social cohesion** (see ACCTING's factsheet with recommendations for public civil society partnership for behavioural change. Such collaborations can help address barriers to participation and ensure that the benefits of commons are shared across diverse populations. To support self-governance effectively, municipalities and NGOs can **co-develop frameworks where responsibilities are shared transparently, balancing community-driven management with necessary institutional support.** This ensures that the self-governance model respects the autonomy of commons-based initiatives while recognising the role of municipalities in facilitating resources, legal protections, and capacity-building opportunities.

Introduce pilot programmes targeting different vulnerable groups

Local authorities should use pilot programmes to engage vulnerable groups. These programmes should focus on developing tailored activities at suitable sites for different vulnerable groups, such as single mothers, children with disabilities, and ex-inmates, emphasising education on sustainability, shared resource management, and the cultural and political importance of commons. To assess the impacts of the programme during this phase, authorities can use mixed-method approaches, such as surveys to measure changes in participants' understanding of sustainability, focus groups to gather qualitative

insights on behavioural changes, and pre- and post-programme evaluations to track shifts in community engagement and attitudes toward nature. Feedback from these pilot programmes will allow for a broader policy to support commons for the vulnerable groups.

Provide financial, infrastructural, and human resource support

Municipalities should recognise community-managed resources, such as urban gardens, shared mobility systems, and other commons, as essential contributors to sustainability and social equity. This recognition would translate into tangible support mechanisms, including financial, infrastructural, and human resource assistance, to empower communities in managing and sustaining these resources effectively. Additionally, municipalities should implement legal and policy frameworks to protect and reclaim commons, ensuring they are safeguarded against privatisation or exploitation.

Highlight outcomes to inspire scaling and replicability

Municipalities can play a key role in supporting initiatives that showcase and disseminate the positive outcomes of commons-based projects. By providing platforms for community initiatives to share their experiences, good practices, and success stories, municipalities contribute to raising awareness and fostering inspiration for similar efforts elsewhere. Such support enables local initiatives to share their stories through local channels, EU platforms, and collaborative networks, demonstrating the value of commons in achieving social equity and sustainability.

Better Stories

In ACCTING, we look for inspiring bottom-up initiatives as '*better stories*', a concept borrowed from Dina Georgis³⁶. Here, these refer to promising practices supporting the idea of commons in (urban and peri-urban) areas in their operations that can instil ideas for how to advance individual and collective behavioural change as envisioned by the Green Deal. The project also supported its own pilot projects, aimed at the promotion of sustainable behaviours through participation in commons. A number of these projects and better stories are presented below:

Dock project in Greece³⁷

Dialogue & Action Against Wildfires is a pilot project funded by ACCTING and led by Dock, it focused on a cluster of four mountainous villages in Messinia, Peloponnese, Greece. With 570 inhabitants and 3.900 hectares rich in natural and cultural heritage sites, these villages served as a microcosm that could model wildfire resilience for similarly at-risk territories. It

³⁶ [Georgis, D. \(2013\). *The better story: Queer affects from the Middle East*. Suny Press.](#)

³⁷ <https://dock-sse.org/project/empowering-local-communities/>

used bottom-up approaches to co-create scenario for handling disaster. The pilot utilised the concept of commons to deal with the issue of natural disaster

Bela Flor Respira³⁸

Bela Flor Respira (The Lovely Flower Breathes) is an urban community garden initiative which combines environmental restoration with community-building efforts. It engages participation from across the entire community, including residents of all ages, volunteers, members of the academic community from the University of Lisbon, and the Municipality of Campolide. Targeting low-income individuals, the elderly, immigrants, and women, the initiative fosters inclusivity and empowers the local community. Through planting, cultivation, and skills transfer, Bela Flor Respira raises environmental awareness, promotes sustainable consumption, and facilitates intergenerational knowledge exchange.

Echoversity project in Zagori, Greece³⁹

The Echoversity, pilot project in Zagori leveraged the concept of commons by integrating community-driven approaches to conserve biodiversity and preserve intangible cultural heritage. By involving local stakeholders in mapping pastoral trails, recording biodiversity through soundscape technology, and organising participatory workshops, the initiative empowered residents to take ownership of ecological preservation. Women pastoralists played a pivotal role as ambassadors of biodiversity and cultural identity, showcasing their contributions through storytelling and locally inspired products.

Mapko project in the Czech Republic⁴⁰

The "Mapko" pilot project highlights the role of community gardens as commons spaces that bridge social and economic inequalities in the Czech Republic. Targeting vulnerable populations, such as migrants, low-income households, and individuals with disabilities, the project fostered social cohesion and environmental sustainability through outreach efforts like multilingual campaigns, partnerships with over 30 NGOs, and participatory events such as community-stakeholder meetings and gardening workshops. The project's platform, which registered 59 new gardens, attracted over 6,500 users in 2024, and offered features like a knowledge bank and user recognition badges to enhance collaboration. Social cohesion was further strengthened by providing childcare support and addressing linguistic barriers, enabling broader participation and promoting female leadership. Challenges such as leadership turnover were mitigated with mentorship programmes, while agreements with municipalities and private developers secured long-term sustainability, including integrating gardens into urban planning.

IncLucivEC's Awards project in Spain⁴¹

The IncLucivEC's Awards, an ACCTING funded pilot project, exemplifies the power of commons in fostering inclusive energy communities. By creating a platform for collective

³⁸ <https://belaflorespira.wixsite.com/agrofloresta>

³⁹ <https://accting.eu/selected-pilot-projects/echoversity-an-innovative-participatory-biodiversity-conservation-project/>

⁴⁰ <https://accting.eu/selected-pilot-projects/mapko-connects-community-gardens/>

⁴¹ <https://accting.eu/selected-pilot-projects/inclusivecs-awards-encouraging-the-inclusion-of-vulnerable-groups-in-energy-communities/>

learning and collaboration, the initiative empowered over 200 participants to share experiences and tackle systemic barriers in developing community energy models. Through workshops, peer-to-peer exchanges, and the production of a practical policy brief, the pilot bridged gaps in knowledge and inclusivity among volunteers. It also established enduring communication channels, ensuring continued collaboration among diverse energy communities. These efforts not only highlighted the potential of shared resources to address energy poverty but also strengthened social cohesion and inclusiveness, paving the way for a more equitable energy transition.

Relevant Green Deal policy areas

Farm to fork strategy: Community gardens and urban farming initiatives align with the Farm to Fork Strategy by promoting sustainable food production within cities, improving food security, and encouraging healthier dietary habits.

Biodiversity and ecosystem protection: Urban commons foster local biodiversity, restore ecosystems, and enhance the resilience of urban environments. By connecting children and families with nature, these initiatives promote a deeper appreciation for biodiversity and environmental stewardship.

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Further development

The aim of the ACCTING project is to address the impact of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups, prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels for an inclusive and equal Green Deal. The seven factsheets developed in this cycle of the project serve as actionable recommendations that will be further promoted among the target audiences and stakeholders. This advocacy will be carried out based on the advocacy plan that is prepared as a part of WP7 of the project.

These factsheets encapsulate ACCTING's commitment to provide in-depth understanding of inequalities caused or worsened by the Green Deal, provide examples of bottom-up initiatives that have positive impact and provide recommendations to target groups for improvement. Further by promoting these recommendations among local NGOs, CSOs and local authorities the advocacy action will ensure that these recommendations are translated into tangible policy innovations and grassroots initiatives.

This holistic approach of ACCTING not only amplifies the voices of those often excluded from decision-making processes but also drives systemic change by embedding social justice and sustainability when combating climate change and environmental crises.